

**Cultural Synthesis in Iranian Graphic Design:
A Fusion of Tradition and Modernity**

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Abstract

This research foregrounds the critical role of graphic design in navigating cultural identity amidst globalization through the lens of Iranian graphic design. It examines the dynamic interplay between tradition and modernity, particularly highlighting how traditional Persian art and calligraphy are integrated into contemporary design practices. This study explores the evolution of graphic design in Iran, influenced by significant political, societal, and economic shifts, especially over the last century. Despite historical upheavals, including various invasions and cultural integrations from the Far East to Europe, Iranian design has resiliently maintained its Persian roots. The research delves into the reinterpretation of traditional motifs—such as Persian miniatures, carpets, and calligraphy—in today’s design context, emphasizing their enduring cultural and symbolic significance. Utilizing an extensive literature review, case studies and archival research, this study provides insights into the fusion of historical elements with contemporary design practices. By analyzing the transformative role of traditional arts in modern Iranian graphic design, this research highlights graphic design’s pivotal role as a mediator in understanding and expressing cultural identity, contributing significantly to the discourse on cultural synthesis and social critique within graphic design.